

APPLICABILITY OF WEIBULL STRENGTH DISTRIBUTION FOR CELLULOSE FIBERS WITH HIGHLY NON-LINEAR BEHAVIOUR

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SUMMARY

It is shown that the tensile strength of cellulose fibers at a fixed length follows two-parameter Weibull distribution. However, due to non-linear behaviour of cellulose fibers, size effect of strength is better captured by the three-parameter Weibull distribution. Single fiber as well as bundle tensile tests are performed, effect of moisture and strain rate on fiber strength is estimated.

Keywords: Weibull distribution, cellulose fibers, single fiber test, bundle test

INTRODUCTION

Natural fibers, such as flax and hemp for example, are widely used as reinforcement in polymer composites. Although there is a large potential in using these fibers for creating high performance composites, there are still some problems associated with these reinforcements which delay wider usage of such materials for structural applications. Some of the problems to mention are: non-uniform quality of filaments (not only within the batch but also from batch to batch), limited fiber length (often fibers are too short to be effective), poor fiber/matrix adhesion etc. One of the weakest points of natural fiber composites is considered to be low impact strength which is likely to result from the complex internal structure of these fibers. Nevertheless, all the disadvantages are often compensated for by the environmental issues, natural fibers being environmentally friendlier than their synthetic, man made counterparts. However, recently another type of man made fibers have emerged as a possible alternative to glass fibers - spun cellulose fibers. Although being man made, their raw material originates from nature and they possess many advantages of the man-made industrial fibers, such as uniform and controlled quality (in terms of dimensions and mechanical properties) and possibility to obtain long continuous fibers which can be arranged in fabrics and used to manufacture composites with highly oriented filaments. This makes them a very promising alternative for producing high performance composites. As a matter of fact there are results which show that short cellulose fiber composites are very competitive in terms of mechanical properties with short glass fiber reinforced polymers [1-3]. But in order to design high performance structural material there is still a need to investigate properties and performance of these fibers which is the main purpose of this study.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

It is widely accepted that the strength of fibers used in composites is treated statistically, for example, glass and carbon fiber strength is rather well described by the three-parameter Weibull distribution:

$$P(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left[-\frac{l}{l_0} \left(\frac{\sigma - \sigma_0}{\beta} \right)^\alpha \right] \quad (1)$$

σ – applied stress, P - probability of fiber failure, l – fiber length, l_0 – reference length, α – shape parameter, β – scale parameter, σ_0 – location parameter. Once Weibull distribution parameters (α , β , σ_0) are known it is possible to predict average strength of a fiber of any length:

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = \sigma_0 + \beta \left(\frac{l}{l_0} \right)^{-1/\alpha} \Gamma \left(1 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \right) \quad (2)$$

If $\sigma_0 = 0$ then Eq. 1 becomes two-parameter Weibull distribution:

$$P(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left[-\frac{l}{l_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\beta} \right)^\alpha \right] \quad (3)$$

and average strength is calculated as:

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = \beta \left(\frac{l}{l_0} \right)^{-1/\alpha} \Gamma \left(1 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \right) \quad (4)$$

This distribution (Eq. 3) is commonly used to describe strength distribution for brittle synthetic fibers (e.g. glass and carbon fibers).

The most direct experimental method to obtain Weibull parameters is single fiber tensile test. Large number of fibers should be tested and probability of failure is obtained as:

$$P = \frac{i - .3}{n + .4} \quad (5)$$

where i – the i -th number in ascendingly ordered fiber strength data and n – total number of tested fibers. These results then are plotted in the double logarithmic axes: $\ln(-\ln(1-P))$ vs $\ln(\sigma)$, and Weibull parameters are obtained from the linear equation which is used to fit these experimental results.

However, it is possible to obtain Weibull parameters from the bundle tests as well. It is assumed that fibers in the bundle are acting as elementary filaments and that there is no friction between the fibers. If these assumptions are true then load-strain curve of bundle tests has “bell-shape”, typical curve from fiber bundle tensile test is presented in Fig. 1. In this case probability of failure is obtained as: $P = 1 - F/F^*$ and the rest of

analysis is similar to that of single fiber tensile test (in this case either strain is used instead of stress or stress is obtained by multiplying strain and fiber stiffness).

Figure 1. Typical load-strain curve (blue line) from bundle tensile test.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials

The type of the fibers is “Cordenka 700 Super 3”. General characteristics of the reinforcement are available from manufacturer [4]: linear nominal density 2440 dtex; number of filaments in the bundle 1350; twist 100 t/m.

Experimental procedure

Single fiber tensile test

Single fiber tests are performed according to the ASTM D 3379-75 Standard [5]. Single fibers were manually separated from the bundles. Fiber ends were glued onto a paper frame. Two gauge length specimens were prepared with fiber length of 20 and 50 mm respectively. Tension tests were carried out on an electromechanical tensile machine Instron 4411 equipped with load cell of 5N and pneumatic grips. During mounting the specimens were handled only by the paper frame. After the clamping of the ends of the paper frame by the grips of the test machine, frame sides were carefully cut in the middle. The tests were displacement-controlled with the loading rate of 10 %/min. Images of the fiber in the frame (schematic drawing and photograph) and mounted in the machine with cut paper frame are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Schematic drawing (left) and photograph (middle) of the single fiber specimen. Photograph of the fiber mounted in the pneumatic grips (paper frame is cut).

Three batches of single fiber specimens were tested in total: one batch of 20 mm (30 fibers) and 2 batches of 50 mm (24 fibers in each batch). Fiber spool was stored for approximately 6 weeks in the room with relative humidity of 45-55% and at temperature of 22-25°C. The tensile tests were performed at the same conditions. Therefore, these fibers are considered to be “reference” batch (further designated as “Reference” or “R”). Two reference batches were tested (20 mm and 50 mm). One batch of fibers (50 mm) was dried in the oven at 50°C for 24h and then tested (this batch is designated as “Dried” or “D”). Tensile tests of dried fibers were performed immediately after the fibers were removed from the oven (the whole procedure starting from the moment when fiber is taken from the oven to the end of the tensile test took approximately 2-3 min). Additionally to the results obtained from single fiber tensile tests performed within this study, data from [3] was also analyzed.

Fiber bundle tensile test

Fiber bundle tests are much easier to perform than single fiber tensile tests, mostly due to specimen preparation procedure and specimen handling. Although information from bundle experiments is not as detailed and in some cases as reliable as from single fiber tensile tests, bundle tests give good estimation of fiber properties, particularly strength. Schematic representation of bundle specimen is shown in Fig. 3: every bundle is fitted with wooden end tabs by gluing bundle ends in between flat pieces of wood (Araldite 2011 two-component epoxy resin was used as glue).

Tests were performed on the same tensile machine as single fiber tensile tests but this time the machine was equipped with mechanical grips and load cell of 500N, loading rate of 10%/min was used (displacement controlled test).

Three batches of “Reference” (or “R”) fibers (three lengths: 50, 100 and 200 mm) were tested in order to compare fiber strength values obtained from bundle tests with results from single fiber tensile experiments. Two batches (50 and 100 mm) of fiber bundles were dried (50°C for 24h) and then tested (designated as “Dried” or “D”). Fiber bundles were tested immediately after they were removed from the oven (within 3-4 minutes).

All, except one, batches of bundles were tested at the loading rate of 10 %/mm. One batch of fiber bundles of 50 mm was also tested at a higher strain rate of 100 %/min (these tests are designated as “F” or “Fast”). Most of the batches of bundles contained at least 5 specimens (a couple of batches consisted only of 4 samples).

Figure 3. Schematic drawing of the bundle specimen.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fiber diameter

Limited number of measurements of fiber diameter was performed by use of optical microscopy. Based on these measurements average value of diameter was estimated to

be $d_f=12.5 \mu\text{m}$. It should be noted that variation of diameter from fiber to fiber as well as along the fiber was rather small (within $0.1\text{-}0.2 \mu\text{m}$) thus it was decided to use the same value of diameter for stress calculations for all fibers.

Single fiber tensile tests

Reference fibers

Experimental results of the tensile tests along with the fitted Weibull distributions for fibers of 20 and 50 mm length are presented in Fig. 4(a). These results show that both, the experimental and the theoretical (Eq. 3), strength distributions for the fibers of different length are almost coinciding. The reason for such behaviour is probably related to the non-linear ductile behaviour of these filaments. Typical Load-Displacement curves for some of the 50 mm fibers are shown in Fig. 4(b). This graph shows that the load-displacement (or stress-strain) curve for these fibers is bi-linear with a “knee” on the curve at approximately 0.7 mm of displacement (which corresponds to 1.4 % strain). It should be noted that prediction in Fig. 4(a) is made by using Weibull parameters obtained for each fiber length individually (Eq. 3 with $l=l_0$). However, if Weibull parameters obtained from one fiber length are used to predict strength distribution for fiber with another length (Eq. 3 with $l_0=1 \text{ mm}$) the correlation between predicted and experimental results is not that good as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 4. Strength distribution (a) and stress-strain curves (b) from single fiber test.

Figure 5. Comparison of 20 and 50 mm fiber data (Eq. 3, $l_0=1 \text{ mm}$).

Since it is known that Weibull distribution is appropriate for brittle materials which behave in linear and elastic manner, the reason for discrepancy between experimental results and theoretical predictions can be tentatively related to non-linear ductile behaviour of Cordenka fibers (see Fig. 4(b)).

Three-parameter Weibull distribution

The statistical treatment of fiber strength is sought not only to describe strength scatter but also to predict the variation of strength with fiber length. The latter cannot be reliably done by means of Eq. 3 as follows from the results presented in Fig. 5 and also the data in [3]. As an alternative, we consider Weibull three-parameter distribution, Eq. 1, and evaluate its parameters using the graphs of empirical strength distributions reported in [3] at four Cordenka fiber lengths. The location parameter is chosen as the lower limit of strength in the graphs, $\sigma_0 = 645$ MPa. The remaining parameters are estimated by fitting Eq. 1 to the empirical distributions, producing $\alpha = 6.9$ and $\beta = 303$ MPa ($l_0=1$ mm as above). Comparison of the variation of average fiber strength according to [3] with the respective theoretical relation Eq. 2 is shown in Fig. 6. It is seen that Eq. 2 provides reasonable agreement with the test data, although it does not capture correctly the vanishing length effect on strength at $l \geq 20$ mm seen in Figs. 4a and Fig. 6.

Figure 6. The dependence of mean strength on fiber length. The experimental data are borrowed from [3].

Effect of humidity

Experimental results and Weibull plot for dried and reference 50 mm long fibers are presented in Fig. 7. The summary of the results for reference and dried fibers are presented in the Table 1 for easier comparison.

These results show that strength of the fibers after drying is reduced by 10%. Moreover, shape parameter of Weibull distribution is lower which means that strength distribution is wider (experimental scatter is larger). It is a little surprising that drying of the fibers reduces their strength, since it is known that moisture usually degrades properties of natural fibers with high cellulose content. The possible reason for such behavior might be initiation of microscopic defects on the fiber surface during the drying. Thus, even

though strength of the material might be increasing with reduction of moisture content (drying) the presence of surface defects leads to premature failure of the filament.

Figure 7. Comparison of strength distribution of dried and reference 50 mm long fibers.

Table 1. Summary of results from single fiber tensile tests (Eq. 3, $l_0=1$ mm).

Batch	Number of samples	Weibull parameters		Strength, Exp [MPa]	Strength, W. [MPa]	Strain, Exp [%]
		α	β , [MPa]			
20 mm "R"	30	10.6	1031	742 ± 79	741	10.72 ± 1.76
50 mm "R"	24	10.8	1119	743 ± 77	742	10.22 ± 1.78
50 mm "D"	24	7.8	1175	670 ± 97	669	9.88 ± 1.95

Bundle tensile tests

Reference bundles

Stress of the bundles was calculated by using number of fibers in the bundle and average fiber diameter (simply by multiplying fiber cross-section by number of fibers in the bundle). Strain was calculated from displacement of cross-head of the machine. Compliance of the machine was accounted for in evaluation of strain and stiffness. The typical stress-strain curves for each batch of reference bundles of different length are presented in Fig. 8(a). The average results for the reference bundles are summarized in the Table 2.

There are several important observations that follow from these results. First of all, stress-strain curves for bundles (Fig. 8) are very similar to load-deflection curves obtained from single fiber experiments (see Fig. 4(b)). As a matter of fact the shape of these curves is almost identical (behaviour of bundles is also highly non-linear). Secondly, the shape of these curves is very different from the theoretical curve for bundle test presented in Fig. 1. It is reasonable to conclude that fibers in the bundle do not work independently of each other, most likely due to rather high yarn twist and resulting friction between fibers. Because of that bundle behaves very similarly to the single fiber and it is highly complicated to derive any statistical information from these tests. Moreover, results in Fig. 8(a) show that stress-strain curves for bundles of different length are almost identical, which also indicates that size effect of strength for these fibers is not observed. Therefore, further on the statistical effects will be neglected and average strength of the bundles will be estimated from a limited number of specimens (at least 4-6 valid tests).

Figure 8. Comparison of reference bundle tests for different sample lengths (a) and comparison of reference and dried bundles (b); typical stress-strain curves.

Table 2. Summary of the results of reference bundles with different length.

Batch	Number of samples	Strength [MPa]	Strain [%]	Stiffness [GPa]
50B mm "R"	6	562 ± 26	8.97 ± 0.59	16.1 ± 1.0
100B mm "R"	5	597 ± 21	9.02 ± 0.21	15.8 ± 0.4
200B mm "R"	4	545 ± 27	8.10 ± 0.42	15.9 ± 0.2

The average properties of fiber bundles of different length appear to be very similar (see Table 2). Stiffness of all bundles is almost exactly the same, strain at failure and strength of 50 and 100 mm long fibers is also almost equal, although strain at failure and strength of 200 mm long bundle is slightly lower. But it should be noted that for the longest bundles only 4 tests were performed and one of them was excluded from calculation of strength and strain at failure due to obviously premature failure.

Stiffness of the bundles here was calculated by linear fit of the experimental results within the linear part of stress-strain curve (values within 30-130 MPa of stress were selected for these calculations).

As expected values obtained from bundle tests are lower than those from single fiber tensile experiments. Comparison of 50 mm long fibers and bundles shows that strength of bundles is lower by approximately 32%, strain at failure by 14% and stiffness by 22% than the same properties obtained from single fiber tests (for comparison purposes stiffness of fibers from [2] is used). It should be noted that strain from single fiber tests was not corrected with respect to the compliance of the tensile machine, therefore actual difference of strain at failure of bundles and single fibers might be much smaller.

Dried bundles

Typical stress-strain curves for dried bundles and reference bundles of the same length are presented in Fig. 8(b). Shapes of the curves are very similar to those of reference bundles. The average results for the dried bundles are summarized in the Table 3.

Table 3. Summary of the results of dried bundles with different length.

Batch	Number of samples	Strength [MPa]	Strain [%]	Stiffness [GPa]
50B mm "D"	5	685 ± 29	9.36 ± 0.46	15.2 ± 0.5
100B mm "D"	5	701 ± 30	9.11 ± 0.53	16.2 ± 0.8

It has to be noted (see Fig. 8(b)) that dried bundles perform better than reference specimens. Both, strength and strain at failure of dried specimens are higher than those for reference material. Strength is increased by approximately 15-18%, whereas strain is increased only by 2-4% (it can be actually considered the same within experimental scatter). The stiffness of the bundles did not change, it is actually a little bit lower for dried bundles than for reference materials but considering experimental scatter these values are almost the same. These graphs also show that in case of dried bundles, similar as for reference specimens, there is no significant difference between behavior of 50 and 100 mm long bundles.

Increase of mechanical properties of the fiber bundles due to drying contradicts results obtained from single fiber tensile tests where drying reduced strength of the fibers. As was already stated earlier, one can speculate that drying in general is advantageous for fiber properties because moisture content is reduced but in the same time it introduces critical defects in the fiber. Therefore single fiber might be overall better in terms of mechanical properties but it fails earlier due to “newly initiated” critical flaws, whereas in case of the bundles fibers are working all together due to high twist. Thus, even if there are newly developed defects in the fibers and some fail earlier, because of the twist and high friction, stress is transferred along the fiber and critical defect is somewhat shielded by stress redistribution to other neighboring fibers. This would be very similar if bundle were impregnated by resin which would assure stress transfer along the whole fiber length and stress redistribution to the neighboring filaments.

Strain rate effect

Typical stress-strain curves for 50 mm long bundles tested at 10%/min and 100%/min are presented in Fig. 9 and averaged data are summarized in Table 4. These results show that increase of strain rate causes increase of strength and strain at failure by approximately 8-10%. It should be noted that stiffness of the bundles did not change with increase of strain rate, as a matter of fact it slightly decreased (although it is the same if experimental scatter is considered).

Figure 9. Comparison of reference and “Fast” bundle tests.

Table 4. Summary of the results of reference and “Fast” bundle tests (50 mm).

Batch	Number of samples	Strength [MPa]	Strain [%]	Stiffness [GPa]
50B mm "R"	6	562 ± 26	8.97 ± 0.59	16.1 ± 1.0
50B mm "F"	4	617 ± 35	9.66 ± 0.46	15.5 ± 0.4

Effect of strain rate indicates that these materials are not only non-linear (as seen from stress-strain curves) but there might be very significant visco-elastic and probably visco-plastic behaviour present.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Single filaments and bundles of Cordenka 700 Super 3 fibers have been tested. Results of single fiber tensile tests showed that within one batch of fibers (of the same length) their strength distribution follows two-parameter Weibull distribution. However, in order to predict fiber strength dependence on length three-parameter Weibull distribution appears preferable. This is most likely due to highly non-linear behavior of the fibers.

Fiber bundles cannot be used to directly evaluate Weibull parameters of the fibers due to high twist and resulting friction between the fibers. Nevertheless, bundles gave very stable results with rather low experimental scatter. Shape of stress-strain curves of bundles resembles those obtained from single fiber tests, which confirms that all fibers in bundle work together.

Drying of fibers resulted in reduction of properties of single fibers by approximately 10%, whereas strength of bundles increased after drying. This can be attributed to the fact that strength of a single fiber is governed by the critical defects which can develop during the drying, whereas in case of bundles single fiber failure does not lead to the failure of the whole yarn but rather stress is redistributed to the neighboring fibers, similarly to the case of bundle impregnated with resin.

Results of this study showed that fibers are highly non-linear. Most likely these fibers would exhibit significant visco-elastic (or/and visco-plastic) behavior. More detailed work is needed in order to arrive at definitive conclusions about this topic.

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